
LOCAL KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION TO COPE WITH CLIMATE-CHANGE FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS: A CASE STUDY OF ALMORA DISTRICT

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Introduction

Agriculture and food security are among the major casualties of climate change in hill eco-system. Strategies such as adopting necessary mitigation measures in a local level with widespread awareness on this issue are needed. The present paper deals with activities in a form of mitigation strategies adopted by local farmers in a period of three years from 2012 to 2014 to cope with the changing climate conditions. Rural land-users in many developing areas are facing increasing challenges to their day-to-day livelihoods (Francis, 2000). Himalaya has various types of agricultural zones like plains, hills, mid hills, high hills and mountains. Changes in agri-zones of Himalayan ecosystem lead to the changes in cropping pattern in different zones. Climatic parameters have potential impact to change the ecological distribution of agricultural crops. If shifting of climatic zones occurs rapidly due to climate change, extinction of biodiversity might be severe. Effects are likely to be on herbs, pasturelands, tree lines and livestock (Malla, 2008). Micro-level monitoring of land use and innovative agricultural planning methods has become essential part of hill agriculture (Singh, 1992). In Himalaya increase in temperature cause more damage to agricultural sectors in Terai region and will be more favorable to agriculture in the hills. The focus of agriculture in the area is slowly shifting from traditional cereal crops to high-value cash crops farming such as fruits and vegetables (Singh and Heitala, 2014). This transformation from subsistence systems to commercial agriculture poses new challenges for improving and maintaining productivity and quality. People of the hills are changing their traditional methods of crop production under the changing climatic conditions and adapting new methods of agriculture with focus on organic farming. They are enhancing their local knowledge in an innovative and sustainable manner. So it becomes very essential to study their changing farming strategies and its impacts on livelihood.

The main objective of the study is to identify some locally adapted innovative technologies to respond to climate

change and to study their adaptation methods to enhance food security.

Methodology

Five villages named Akhoria Naugaon, Ucha wahan, Chasila, Gopalgoun, Seema and Kothyu of Almora district of Kumaun region has been selected for the study by taking following of the criteria:

- Representative rain-fed mountain villages where agriculture is still mainstay of livelihood.
- Accessibility and coordination of the villages.
- Availability of experienced, innovative and elderly farmers has also been taken into account.

Total 200 farmers (100 women) were studied for using Participatory Methods. Farmers and community groups were studied to evaluate their innovations for adapting to climate change and interviews were carried out with other stakeholders, e.g. academia, extension workers, private entrepreneurs. The baseline studies, focus group discussions and field monitoring were carried out.

Results and Discussion

The study brings out following observations:

- Initially five innovations were identified and disseminated. One innovation addressed the problem of white grub, a major problem in the fields. It was noticed by a farmer that the plantation of *Akarkara* plant in and around the agriculture field reduced the number of white grub in the field. This was tried out by a number of farmers who got success in keeping white grub away. During the survey total 62 farmers of 5 selected villages tried this technique and found it was effective in saving their crops from damage by white grub (Insect).
- Small agriculture implements like *syahi* plough, *darati*, *kudal*, weeding Rake, Line maker, Hand fork, *Khurpi* and hand hoe which were improved versions of traditional implements were tried out in four villages. Seeing the good results of these implements, 110 farmers of 6 villages are using them.

- In situ water conservation through bunding, digging trenches around the terrace fields has been found effective method for water conservation and controlling the topsoil erosion. Top soil, the major and important part of soil composition humus which supported the agricultural crops was protected by the bunds. During the 3 years total 46 farmers of 2 villages tried in situ water conservation technique in more than 100 *Nali* (2 Ha).
- Farmers prepared liquid manure and tried out as growth promoters for vegetable crops. They also found that it reduced the risk of insect and disease attacks to vegetable crops. A total of 25 farmers from 3 project villages made liquid manure and used it in vegetable crops during last 3 years. This practice is still going on and expanding.
- The main objective of experimenting with drought tolerant varieties was to identify different crops which were suitable for adoption in different micro-climatic areas in respect of their survival, yield potential and tolerance to stress conditions. During the last three years (2012-2014) four crops Paddy, Wheat, Barley and Maize under cereals, two crops *Ragi* and *Jhingora* under millets, six crops Soyabean, *Bhatt*, *Gahat*, *Arhar*, Gram, and Lentil under pulses and two oilseed crops yellow Mustard and Toria were experimented. Results of these crops were quite encouraging in comparison to the varieties being used by the farmers. A total 110 farmers from 5 villages comprising 48 women and 62 men farmers in 20.64 hectare area were directly involved in joint experimentation during the survey. 95 farmers of the villages were also benefited by adopting the learning.

Small Scale Community Innovations

Besides this, a few other local innovations were also identified and developed and documented. These pertained to growing of *Tarud*: a lesser known root vegetable found in the wild, use of waste cloth from a tailoring shop to shape a trellis for growing creeper vegetables, innovation for better adaptation of System of Rice Intensification (SRI) method to the farming practices of mountain farmers, growing of marigold for keeping away pests, cultivation of big cardamom as a new crop, moisture conservation for onion nursery, creeper crop seed germination in poly bag, protection of onion nursery by hailstorm, water conservation at source by digging percolation pits, solution to seed rotting problem in potato, locally made paddy thresher and fish rearing pond. The perception of the villagers

was also documented. 55 households participated with a coverage area of approximately 500 running meter grass plantation. This kind of effort secured farmers' additional income from agriculture field. New fruit and forage plants were tried by the community in three hectare area with participation of 90 farmers. 36 farmers of 5 villages took up beekeeping with total of 48 boxes as an additional activity. Vegetable farming was tried in village Bhatoli.

Conclusion

Mountain agriculture is at risk due to climate change and induced disasters. Agriculture as a livelihood option is rated very low. However, many people continue to work in their land in absence of other options. Most of the farmers today in rural areas are women. They have limited exposure and less recognition. The recognition for innovation, support for sharing, coming together for joint venture and trials for innovation and adaptation to climate change has been very inspirational for the farmers, especially the women. In the villages, there are many enthusiastic farmers who are hopeful of sustained livelihoods from agriculture and willing to take more initiatives. As a facilitator and supporter the role of INHERE is very instrumental and appreciable. This community group has conducted various orientation and training programmes on Climate Change, Participatory discussion with local farmers for awareness generation which benefited many farmers.

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